

COMMUNITY COLLABORATION AND LEARNING FOR CLIMATE RESILIENCE (COOLER) PROJECT END OF YEAR 1 FINDINGS

Rupu Gupta, PhD
Rupu Gupta Consulting

**FOR UNIVERSITY OF NORTHERN COLORADO
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www.rupuguptaconsulting.com

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The COOLER (Community Collaboration and Learning for Climate Resilience) Project was initiated at the University of Northern Colorado (UNC) in 2023 through a Planning Grant funded by the National Science Foundation (#2228170). It was led by UNC faculty, in collaboration with a community builder and an evaluation partner. The three-year project aims to build a “Learning Ecosystem” composed of UNC students, faculty, and community members, and strengthen society-wide climate change education, resilience, and adaptation through community projects and with stakeholders.

The first year primarily involved planning, development of events, activities, resources, and initiating or growing relationships with the three audiences. This included organizing online platforms for resource sharing, developing project communications plans, and hiring UNC students to join the leadership team for their professional development.

The evaluation aimed to study how COOLER builds a multi-stakeholder learning community to tackle climate resilient priorities in Northern Colorado. It used a community of practice framework to understand how the project fosters learning and exchange among a group interested in a specific topic of interest (e.g., local climate resilience). In the first year, a qualitative needs assessment was conducted with the UNC faculty who participated in Climate Conversation workshops, and students who joined the leadership team.

Key findings

Faculty hoped to gain interdisciplinary perspectives and resources on climate change education to provide students a holistic perspective on the topic. To help alleviate students’ emotional toll, they wanted to help them identify solutions. Initial conversations with peers involved getting to know more about each other’s work, and expanding their knowledge of climate issues and teaching approaches. They looked forward to ongoing engagement with each other, including identifying a collaborative project. Faculty described how the project could contribute to local discourse and action to create a climate resilient Greeley, by impacting its natural, built infrastructure, and residents’ personal capacities.

Students on the leadership team appreciated the new knowledge and information they gained as well as being part of a community with a shared interest in addressing climate change. Their biggest impacts were in gaining hands-on experiences about the complex and iterative processes involved in collaborative climate work. They described a sense of pride and ownership in shaping COOLER. They had also learned about the interpersonal nature of climate work, needing to work with people external to the project team.

Implications for the Future

In its first year, COOLER had made observable strides to engage UNC faculty and students in learning about the multiple pathways to understand and address local climate change impacts. The first stage of a community of practice was observed among faculty, with interactions to learn about peers’ expertise. Student leaders had grown a range of capacities encompassing knowledge, ability, and confidence, to address climate impacts through their specific skillsets. Attention to the multiple aspects of a “resilient” community among faculty and students indicated opportunities for COOLER to focus on additional topic and focus areas. Recommendations were made for the subsequent years to strengthen engagement with UNC faculty, students, and to extend the connections with external, community partners.

THE COOLER PROJECT

The COOLER (Community Collaboration and Learning for Climate Resilience) Project was initiated at the University of Northern Colorado (UNC) in the summer of 2023 through a Planning Grant funded by the National Science Foundation (#2228170). The project was led by faculty from UNC with expertise in climate science, geoscience, environmental science, education, and professional development leadership, in collaboration with external consultants in the roles of community builder and evaluation partner.

Over the course of three years, the project's goal is to build a "Learning Ecosystem" that is composed of UNC students and faculty, and community members, and strengthen society-wide climate change education, resilience, and adaptation through community projects and stakeholder engagement. The project objectives are to:

1. Identify how to prepare students to work with community stakeholders on local projects that build community resilience to climate change impacts and ability to adapt.
2. Build expertise about climate change resilience among faculty from a broad array of disciplines.
3. Develop resources for community members to empower them to make decisions and take action around climate change challenges.

Focus of the first year

The first year of COOLER primarily involved planning, development of events, activities, resources, and initiating or growing relationships with the intended audiences. Development of structured platforms for knowledge and resource exchange was a big focus. This included organizing an online platform for the leadership team, developing COOLER branding, launching a newsletter, and creating online platform for resource sharing among faculty.

Students

Another milestone was in hiring a group of three UNC students to join the leadership team to contribute to the project and their professional growth and development. Students worked closely in collaboration with the leadership team, each leading unique aspects of the project, including communications, data analysis, and community engagement efforts.

Faculty

With an internal focus, volunteer learning and networking opportunities were created for faculty across disciplines, for them to engage in conversations about teaching climate change, its local impacts, and their potential role in it. The main approach to engaging faculty was in convening a series of Climate Change Teaching Conversations, each presenting structured opportunities for sharing and learning from each other. These were started in the fall of 2023, with the intent of continuing to provide similar structured and regular sessions for sustained engagement throughout the project.

For both students and faculty, additional events, networking and learning opportunities were created on campus for them to engage in discourse related to climate change, including their knowledge of the phenomenon, its impacts locally, and their potential role in addressing them.

Greeley community members

In parallel, the leadership team initiated identifying external partners who would potentially be interested in collaboration with the COOLER project. Potential partners included community-based organizations, local businesses, municipal and city offices, and others who shared an

interest in addressing local climate priorities through distinct areas of focus (e.g., gardening, composting, environmental and social justice, public health, energy). This first year was seen as an opportunity to create purposeful strategies and approaches to connect with external partners (especially new partners), which involved learning about their priorities tied to climate-related issues and identifying shared interests to shape COOLER.

MONITORING PROGRESS

UNC partnered with an evaluation consultant to understand how the project builds a multi-stakeholder learning community (comprising students, faculty, community groups) that aims to learn about and tackle climate resilient priorities in Northern Colorado. Building on the goals and objectives of COOLER, the evaluation, over the three years, aimed to examine the how the learning community will enable the various groups to:

- Grow their knowledge base about local climate resilient priorities;
- Build agency, self-efficacy, and personal resilience in collaborating on local issues;
- Respectfully engage in equitable exchange and learning; and
- Co-develop community-focused projects to build climate resilience in northern Colorado.

A community of practice (CoP) framework informed the framing of the study (Wenger, Trayner, & de Laat, 2011); where a CoP is defined as “a learning partnership among people who find it useful to learn from and with each other about a particular area”, in this case local climate resilience issues. The evaluation aimed to use the different cycles in the evolution of a CoP (e.g., Immediate value through activities and interactions; Potential value by growing knowledge capital; Applied value when using lessons to change existing practice) to understand how the project helps members learn and be empowered.

The learning community’s engagement among a group with multiple interests and expertise, will be assessed to understand how they develop shared goals and understandings of local climate priorities in respectful and culturally responsive ways (e.g., Gupta, Ardan, & Fraser, 2017); appreciate different perspectives on environment-focused work (Fraser, Gupta, & Krasny, 2014); and conceptualize and build climate justice for a resilient community (Cutter et al. 2008; Gupta, LaMarca, Nock, Flinner, & Attaway, 2023). Personal resilience will be informed by work on optimism and hope for environmental work (Ojala, 2012) and personal resilience to engage in environmental work (Gupta, LaMarca, Rank, Flinner, & Ardan, 2021).

Focus of evaluation

In the first year, the consultant worked closely with the other COOLER team members, including individual conversations with them, to understand and articulate the development of the project focus. Aligned with the ongoing focus of the project on UNC audiences primarily, the evaluation involved a needs assessment to understand how the project started to build a learning community, beginning with two of the three intended audiences. The audiences in this phase were:

- Faculty members who participated in the Climate Change Teaching Conversations workshops initiated in the Fall of 2023 and continuing in spring of 2024
- Students who were hired to join the COOLER leadership team in various capacities

A developmental evaluation approach (Patton, 2011) was used, emphasizing a collaborative approach, and timely feedback in an innovative, dynamic project context. It was also attentive to the intended use of the evaluation through a utilization focused approach (Patton, 2008). To ensure cultural responsiveness throughout, interactions with all stakeholders were attentive to their circumstances and expertise, and involved close observations, careful listening, and facilitation of reciprocal exchange of knowledge (Pipi, Cram, Hawke, Hawke, Huriwai, Matak, T., et al. 2004; Smith, 2005).

METHODOLOGY

Study design

The needs assessment was conducted through a set of virtual focus groups and interviews with the two groups of audiences. Focus groups were the original method of choice for their role in surfacing interpersonal dynamics and narratives of a group of people discussing a common topic or experience (in this case, their experience with the COOLER project). Conducting a focus group involves a qualitative phenomenological approach known as guided existential reflection to capture the deepest understanding of the unique experiences and perspectives of the audiences. This offers a comprehensive understanding of individuals' lived experience by uncovering their hidden assumptions and values by closely examining their perspective of the topic or phenomena of interest (Van Manen, 2002).

Semi-structured focus group protocols and recruitment materials were developed in close collaboration with the COOLER project team. The study was conducted with approval from University of Northern Colorado's institutional Review Board to ensure that it adhered to ethical standards in conducting research with people (protocol #2207041159).

Audiences, recruitment, and evaluation activities

Faculty (n = 3)

All 8 faculty members who participated in the COOLER conversations were initially introduced via email to the evaluator by the project PI. The evaluator followed up and invited the faculty in a blind-copied email to join a virtual focus group. Those interested were asked to indicate their availability in a Doodle poll, to join a 1 hour focus group during one of several time slots spread over 3 days. A total of three faculty filled out the poll. An email confirmation was sent to them, including the Zoom link to join the meeting on the designated time. Of them, two participated in a focus group, and one in an individual interview, to accommodate schedules.

Students (n = 2)

The evaluator had been introduced to the three student leaders in a prior project meeting. As a result, the evaluator directly contacted them via a blind-copied email to invite them to participate in a virtual focus group or interview. Similar to the faculty, they were asked to indicate their availability via a Doodle pool covering the same time slots. Those who filled out the poll were sent a confirmation email, including a Zoom link. Two students participated in the study through individual interviews.

Participation for all audiences was voluntary and they could choose whether to join, and which questions to answer.

Analysis

Even though prior research on communities of practice informed the framing of the evaluation, the analysis took a bottom-up approach that acknowledged the goal in this needs assessment phase. The responses of the participants indicated that the use of the CoP theory would be premature, given that the conversations had begun only recently. For this reason, to identify participants' initial interests, engagement to date, and future expectations, a thematic analysis (Newell, Norris, & Moules, 2017) was conducted to identify, organize, and, describe the themes that emerged from the conversations.

The analysis of both faculty and students' responses examined their initial expectations, motivations, their learning about local climate priorities, and their future engagement and roles in COOLER. Each group's responses were analyzed and coded through an iterative process.

Analysis was conducted by group. First, each group's responses were coded separately. For each group, the main questions guiding the evaluation were used to organize the themes that emerged from the analysis. Responses for each group were kept separate to clearly identify the unique needs, priorities, and learning experiences that were meaningful for their development. This process aimed to provide a holistic picture of groups' experiences, rather than identify consensus, especially in the context of very small sample sizes (Malterud et al., 2016; Schreiber & Asner-Self, 2011). Common themes across groups were discussed in the Implications section of the report, drawing inferences from the findings.

Given the small sample sizes, to protect the confidentiality of the participants, details of faculty and students' disciplinary backgrounds and work foci have not been described. Themes emerging from the analysis of the focus group and interviews have been aggregated and generalized to retain the sentiments and thoughts expressed, while purposefully excluding identifying information.

RESULTS

Faculty

The three faculty members represented different disciplinary backgrounds and were affiliated with departments with varying levels of focus on environmental issues. Similarly, their familiarity with the topic of climate change ranged from it being a personal interest to being an important aspect of their professional work.

Motivations and Interest

Interest in interdisciplinary work related to climate change education motivated faculty to join the COOLER conversations. They wanted to learn from the project PIs, who they felt were recognized on campus for their collaborative work. There was acknowledgement that work related to environmental issues, and especially complex, intractable challenges like climate change, needed insights from various disciplines. For this reason, they wanted to go beyond their own disciplinary siloes and gain knowledge, resources, and ideas to enhance their teaching and research roles.

The need for a broader perspective on addressing climate change was driven in part by some faculty feeling that **students were interested in the topic**. Faculty aimed to provide a holistic framework that highlighted the scientific, social, and economic implications of climate change to explain the problem and identify solutions. They saw their engagement in a learning community to help fill in gaps in their disciplinary foci through insights from other faculty. While these faculty felt student interest in the topic of climate change was high, there were gaps in their knowledge (e.g., confounding weather and climate, not understanding global and temporal impacts).

Additionally, they described students expressing “**eco anxiety**” and **guilt, acknowledging the emotional toll** the enormity of the challenge posed for people and their role in addressing it. To address these experiences, faculty wanted to highlight content to discuss the problem comprehensively, including ways to mitigate impacts.

Access to resources to enhance their teaching about climate change was another reason for faculty interest in the COOLER conversations. They hoped to learn about tools and other resources that could help them provide concrete examples of the ways climate change impacts students’ lives and make the learning more relevant and urgent, also sparking critical thinking about the ways people contribute to climate change and help mitigate it.

Interactions with Other Learning Community Members

The initial conversations they had had starting this year, entailed getting to know each other, including their disciplines, areas of focus, and learning about student interest and baseline knowledge related to climate change, broadly on campus. Through these, they had started to learn about climate related content that was new to them as well as different approaches to teach it in an engaging way (e.g., expanding lectures to include active discussion opportunities). A couple of faculty members mentioned the group discussing the prospect of a collaborative project that they seemed interested in.

Faculty felt that the learning community had shared concerns and interests in addressing climate change and that they would be **open to learning about different perspectives** from each other. However, there was also **concern about navigating differences in opinions if and when they emerged**, especially when they may be driven by moral and emotional reasons.

Most Valuable Impacts

For the most part, faculty expectations of the conversations were being fulfilled. They were starting to make new connections with others with complementary expertise, identify shared interests, and get access to online resources to share and contribute to. In general, they were looking forward to continued interactions with others in the learning community and with other COOLER events in general.

Interest in Future Engagement

Potential for a collaborative project

One of the ways faculty hoped to engage with COOLER in the future was in **developing a shared project**, reflecting the needs of the collective or a subgroup in it. Acknowledging that this would require additional resources, and availability of time, they were at this early phase, expressing interest in exploring the possibility of a joint initiative, and as the need arises, even leading it. Specific projects they would be interested in included a freshman needs assessment around climate change and an interdisciplinary freshman or sophomore course.

Active sharing of resources

They also envisioned taking a more active role in sharing materials/lesson plans with others in the learning community, building on skills and knowledge they gained through their engagement. Of specific interest were evidence-based materials that help faculty communicate effectively about climate change, so students can make thoughtful inferences and draw their own conclusions about environmental impacts.

Perceived Value of COOLER

In general, faculty appreciated the project's innovation in providing the first-ever campus wide initiative to help students and faculty better address climate change. They also described various ways in which they perceived the project could contribute to discourse and action locally to create a climate resilient Greeley.

Conceptualizing Resilience

With a focus on the UNCO campus community, faculty emphasized the need to grow both their own and their students' **personal resilience** as they grappled with addressing the impacts of a changing climate. They described the need for faculty to be part of a supportive community to collectively process their own guilt and grief related to dealing with a changing climate. Acknowledging similar emotional experiences in their students, they aimed to help them by incorporating discussions of actions and resources to mitigate climate change impacts to assuage their helplessness.

Improving the campus' built and natural environment was another way faculty thought about the idea of resilience. They described the need for improved on-campus recycling and trash infrastructure and creating awareness of these facilities, so people could take informed steps to improve the campus.

A broader, integrated systems-level framework was also acknowledged, highlighting the need to make Greeley resilient in interconnected ways. This meant addressing multiple societal systems impacting social, economic, public health, ecological outcomes as they intersected with transportation and energy sectors.

Future Support from COOLER

As they engaged in future conversations with the COOLER learning community faculty hoped for **more opportunities to engage with each other in informal and formal, structured ways**. Through these, they hoped to become more familiar with their colleagues' work to be able to identify the most helpful resources and knowledge to add to their respective climate toolkits.

There was also **interest in a better understanding of the various modes of engagement** COOLER aimed to provide. This information would help faculty plan and prepare better so they can participate effectively in the future.

They also **appreciated the shared depository** in the process of being organized that would help them share relevant knowledge and resources for all to use. They looked forward to interacting more with it in the future.

With an eye to the project's longer-term trajectory, one faculty member drew attention to the reality of this ambitious project in light of the level of funding and other resources UNCO had access to. Their note of caution for the future of the project was **to be strategic and pragmatic about the project's progress**, within the constraints of limited resources for support.

Students

Motivations and Interest

The student leaders were deeply invested in the topic of climate change, applying to join the COOLER team to **advance their professional and personal goals**. They were interested in the opportunity to add to their knowledge of climate change and its impacts, learn about ways to mitigate them, grow their professional experience, and engage with different groups involved in the environmental and climate sector.

Overall Experience with COOLER

Students described their experience in COOLER in very positive terms. They appreciated the **new knowledge and information** they had gained and felt there was good synergy among the project team members. They especially **valued being part of a community** with a common interest in addressing climate change. They enjoyed working with faculty who were also eager to learn in the process. With their peers, they had had somewhat limited interactions. Despite this, they appreciated being able to connect with peers, learn more about each other's areas of interest, and leverage each other's unique skills to advance a specific task.

The specific roles and responsibilities the students took on for the project aligned with their respective skillsets, helping them lead and take ownership of distinct aspects of the project to support the internal team, as well external partners.

Most Valuable Impacts

The biggest impacts students described was in **gaining hands-on experiences** that demonstrated how complex and time-consuming program development and dissemination can be. They had appreciated getting a sense of the iterative process of collaborative work as well as the opportunities for continuous improvement and refinement.

Students also felt that **being part of leadership was a strong influence** in their professional development. Specifically, the opportunity to share their perspectives and ideas and shape the direction of the project had provided them with a sense of pride and ownership.

They were also able to **build on their existing knowledge** of climate change and learn about the various mitigation strategies that could help address climate change impacts like urban heat.

Future engagement with COOLER

As they continued their work, they hoped to hone their experiences further in the specific tasks they were involved in. They also hoped that as new students joined the project, the current students could provide targeted training for the new students to build on the foundation the current cohort had created.

Growth as Climate Stewards

Building capacity to address climate change now and in the future

In their descriptions of how their role empowered them as climate stewards, students underscored the **interpersonal nature of climate education and dissemination**. They described needing to work with people external to their internal project team, and how their role in the project had equipped them to engage in knowledge and resource exchange more effectively.

Reinforcing action and sparking learning

Their personal pro-environmental motivations were also reinforced. This resulted in taking individual actions to reduce their carbon footprint and interpersonal communication in sharing their new climate knowledge in other classes. In parallel, they were gaining a **deeper understanding of the multiple ways people are affected and in turn contribute to climate change**. This was apparent in how students perceived connections between COOLER and efforts to create a just and equitable society. Similarly, they were also acknowledging that engagement with climate action varied, including people for whom it isn't an urgent priority, and also those who intentionally sought out a broad community for joint climate action.

Conceptualizing Resilience

For students, climate resilience in Greeley focused on the **city's built infrastructure and social capital**. They spoke about the ways the city needs to do more to keep buildings cool and address extreme heat without exacerbating existing levels of emissions. They also described the need to affect change by community-driven action to address local impacts of climate change.

Perceived Value of COOLER

Students felt the project would impact Greeley in two ways. One at the UNC campus level, where **faculty would be empowered to discuss and act on climate change** through interdisciplinary, collaborative ways. The other more broadly, at the **level of the city's physical infrastructure**, by catalyzing action to create cooler, more energy efficient buildings to address extreme heat.

Future Career Interests

Students anticipated their new skills and capacities would also help their professional journeys beyond graduation. They felt more prepared and confident about future opportunities,

envisioning better job prospects because of the relevant COOLER experiences. They hoped to replicate their project experiences in future professional contexts, contributing to addressing climate change in similar ways. Depending on the trajectory of the project, they also hoped to engage with it in the future through new or similar roles to their original ones.

IMPLICATIONS FOR FUTURE PHASES

An emerging learning community

The first-year evaluation highlighted the strides made by the COOLER project to engage UNC faculty and students in learning about the multiple pathways to address climate change impacts, local climate priorities, and situating their role and contribution to address them.

For faculty, despite representing just under half the group of all potential participants, their responses likely reflect that of highly invested members, providing valuable insights into their personal experiences, and to some extent also that of the group with which they engaged. Even with this small group, there are indications of interest in a community of practice with other faculty to engage in their own knowledge growth about multi-disciplinary approaches to climate education, and then implementing that learning to provide a holistic educational experience for their students (Wenger, Trayner, & de Laat, 2011).

The COOLER workshops provided a space and structured process to interact with others and get to know more about their work and interests related to climate change. This is indicative of the first phase of a CoP, characterized by *Immediate Value*, when, people recognize the unique knowledge, expertise, or experiences they bring. Even though their interactions have only begun, and they expressed interest in deeper learning about each other, there were indicators of wanting to move further along and foster an engaged CoP. Faculty acknowledged the *Potential Value* of these conversations for their work, and even their *Applied Value*, when they can incorporate multi-disciplinary lessons into their existing teaching to empower their students or work with other faculty on a collaborative project.

Developing future climate leaders

Student leaders had grown a range of capacities encompassing knowledge, ability, and confidence, to address climate impacts through their specific skillsets. It was evident that COOLER played a significant, positive role in impacting students' current and future trajectories. With students engaging with others external to COOLER around climate topics, there may be opportunities to further expand the suite of roles future student leaders can take, including leading active outreach efforts or leading student-centered learning communities, beyond their role in the leadership team.

Multiple aspects of climate resilience

Students and faculty are attentive to distinct aspects of what constitutes a "resilient" community. This ranged from supporting individuals' emotional health, building social capital among community members, improvements in local built and natural infrastructure, to addressing larger systems-level change. While their responses underscore how complicated climate change is, they also indicate topics/foci that COOLER will need to focus on moving forward, as the project works more closely with community partners external to UNC.

Concern about students' and faculty's emotional health was articulated strongly, and is an opportunity for COOLER to provide that communal support. Environmental professionals, and educators, in particular, can benefit greatly from being part of a community of practice with shared interest in addressing climate impacts, while grappling with internalized trauma, grief, and loss (Swim, Geiger, Fraser, & Pletcher, 2017). Focusing on hopefulness and their personal self-efficacy in addressing climate impacts in their own distinct ways is critical to sustain their role as climate stewards (Ojala, 2012).

Recommendations

Based on the results of this year's evaluation, the following recommendations are made for the subsequent phases of COOLER:

Faculty learning community

1. Continue to provide purposeful and regular opportunities for faculty to connect and learn deeply about each other's work. While the workshops were the primary mode of engagement for faculty, encouraging participation in additional COOLER events and offerings, would also foster more informal learning exchanges that they seek.
2. Provide future sessions that focus on the following topical areas of interest:
 - a. Strategies and approaches to help faculty negotiate differences in opinion so they can move past emotional conversations and engage in meaningful ways.
 - b. The interconnectedness of climate change impacts with other relevant social and environmental justice topics to emphasize the broader community impact that COOLER is aiming to have. This aims to expand faculty's understanding of the broader systems-wide connection as well as expand their view of themselves as student-focused only.
 - c. Identify opportunities with and for faculty to build external partnerships, so they are able to interface with the community beyond the UNC campus in addressing local climate impacts.
3. Consider the unique roles and responsibilities of the learning community members' work and priorities (e.g., teaching, research, service) in planning the workshops as well as in providing resources to share among the group.
4. Share additional information on the COOLER model, including about other events, activities, offerings, and their connections to the faculty workshops. This will help faculty get a broader understanding of COOLER's role and offerings in Greeley and enable them to participate more strategically.

Students

5. Explore opportunities for student peer mentorship as newer students join the leadership team. This will enable students from the first cohort to develop additional leadership skills, as they support newer students to identify their unique role.

General

6. Start to brainstorm and identify opportunities to connect the various subgroups within the COOLER learning community as the project moves forward. In this early phase, while different learning communities are being fostered through discrete processes, there is scope to critically think through how to cohesively bring together the different audiences (as appropriate), leveraging the relationships that have already been built.
 - This could entail exploring potential opportunities for students to be the connective thread between learning community faculty members and the external community beyond the campus. This could be a way for one or more student leaders, or learning community faculty members' students to engage more strategically with external partners.

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